

Endoloop Placement is a Novel Technique for Endoscopic Removal of Large Colonic Lipoma: A Case Report

Yeshaswini Reddy^{1*}, Srinivas R Puli¹, Lavneet Chawla¹ and Tulika Chatterjee¹

¹University of Illinois College of Medicine at Peoria, Division of Gastroenterology and Hepatology, Peoria, Illinois, USA

Citation: Reddy Y, Puli SR, Chawla L, Chatterjee T. Endoloop Placement is a Novel Technique for Endoscopic Removal of Large Colonic Lipoma: A Case Report. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour*. 2024;3(2):1-4.

Received Date: 23 February, 2024; **Accepted Date:** 26 February, 2024; **Published Date:** 29 February, 2024

***Corresponding author:** Yeshaswini Reddy, University of Illinois, Peoria, IL 61614, Telephone: +1-309-397-0821, USA.

Copyright: © Reddy Y. et al., Open Access 2024. This article, published in *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour (ICMCRJ)* (Attribution 4.0 International), as described by <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

ABSTRACT

Lipomas in the colon are benign and are often solitary lesions of submucosal origin. Most of the patients with lipomas are asymptomatic as they are small. About 75% of the lipomas measuring greater than 2 cm are at increased risk of symptoms such as abdominal pain, distention, bleeding, intussusception, and obstruction. Giant colonic lipomas measuring greater than 4 cm have been removed surgically, however in recent years endoscopic tools are used for removal of these lipomas with less risks. Endoscopic mucosal resection (EMR) techniques used for this usually require specific equipment and advanced training to perform. Endoscopic ligation is a safe alternative without need for advanced training. We here present a giant symptomatic lipoma causing intussusception removed successfully using this novel endoloop technique.

Keywords: Endoscope; Lipomas; Abdominal pain

CASE REPORT

A 55-year-old female with a history of Breast Cancer that was treated with mastectomy presented with acute abdominal pain for three days with associated constipation and obstipation for two days. Patient had intermittent right flank pain for more than a decade but would resolve within a few minutes and was suspected from her lipoma but did not pursue any treatment at that time. On admission her physical exam was pertinent for diffuse abdominal tenderness. Computerized tomography (CT) of the abdomen pelvis showed colo colonic intussusception at the transverse colon with a fat density mass at the distal end measuring 6.4 cm as the lead point (Figure 1). A colonoscopy showed a 7-8 cm submucosal lesion on a stalk in the transverse colon (Figure 2). This lesion was injected with 3 mL of 1 in 10,000 epinephrine with a scleral needle, and two poly loops were applied to the base of the lesion (Figure 3). The biopsy of the lesion was consistent with Lipoma. Following the procedure, the patient had a resolution of her symptoms. A repeat colonoscopy six months later showed scarring at the area of the Lipoma (Figure 4). Endoscopic therapies are emerging as safe surgical alternatives in treating Colonic lipomas^[1]. So far, both Endoloop and Endoscopic resection techniques have been used to unroof giant

lipomas^[2,3,4]. However, endoloop placement alone can be an effective novel endoscopic technique for lipoma removal without resection, as seen in this patient.

Figure 1: CT Abdomen and Pelvis showing Colocolonic intussusception.

Figure 2: Colonoscopy image of Lipoma with positive pillow sign.

Figure 3: Colonoscopy guided poly loop placement of Lipoma.

Figure 4: Follow-up colonoscopy after six months with scar tissue and no recurrence.

Endoscopic therapies are emerging as safe surgical alternatives in treating Colonic lipomas. Endoloop in combination with Endoscopic resections have been used in literature for unroofing gain lipomas. However endoloop placement alone can be used as an effective novel endoscopic technique for lipoma removal without resection as presented in this case.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST AND FINANCIAL DISCLOSURE

Yeshaswini Reddy, Srinivas R Puli, Lavneet Chawla, and Tulika Chatterjee declare no conflict of interest, grant, or financial disclosure.

Y Reddy: Substantial contribution to the conception of work, acquisition, and interpretation of data for this work. Y Reddy, L Chawla, and T Chatterjee: drafting the work and revising the manuscript. Y Reddy, L Chawla, T Chatterjee, and S Puli: provided final approval of the manuscript for publication. Y Reddy, L Chawla, and T Chatterjee: agree to be accountable for any questions related to the accuracy of the work and investigation. Y Reddy is the Corresponding author and article guarantor.

Informed Consent: We confirm that an informed consent was obtained for publication.

REFERENCES

1. Schopis M, Yang J. Endoscopic Treatment of Intussusception From Massive Colonic Lipomas via Endoscopic Mucosal Resection: A Case Series; ACG Case Rep J. 2019;6:e00177.
2. Cartelle AL, Princess PUY, Erikson JL, Yap. Giant Colonic Lipoma Presenting as Intermittent Colonic Obstruction with Hematochezia; Cureus. 2020;12(11):e11434.
3. Lei Shi, MD, Yuanshun Zhao, MD, PhD, Wen Li, MD. Endoscopic resection of a giant colonic lipoma with endoloop-assisted unroofing technique. A case report; Medicine. 2018;97:e10995.
4. Huang C, Steinhauer C, Bush A, Laczek J. Loop-and-Let-Go: Treatment of a Large Colonic Lipoma After Unsuccessful Unroofing; ACG Case Rep J. 2022;9:e00848.